

POLITICAL SCIENCES

EURASIAN REGIONALISM OF KAZAKHSTAN IN NEW GEOPOLITICAL CONDITIONS

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to analyze the Eurasian vectors of Kazakhstan in the new geopolitical reality, as well as to identify new risks and opportunities. In light of the ongoing geopolitical turbulence, this article delves into Kazakhstan's multifaceted foreign policy, characterized by its intricate relations with major global powers. The recent escalation of the conflict in Ukraine has precipitated significant shifts in the regional and international dynamics, compelling Kazakhstan to navigate a complex landscape of geopolitical challenges and recalibrate its foreign policy strategies. This paper examines the diminishing influence of Russia, traditionally a dominant player in Kazakhstan's foreign policy calculus, against the backdrop of international sanctions and its evolving global stance. Concurrently, we explore the ascending influence of China, which has been expanding its economic and strategic footprint in Central Asia, particularly through initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which significantly impact Kazakhstan's economic and geopolitical orientation.

Furthermore, the paper analyzes the nuanced and increasingly significant role of the collective West, especially the United States and European Union, whose interests and influence in the region exhibit a dynamic interplay of engagement and strategic competition. The analysis underscores how the war in Ukraine has not only reshaped global geopolitical contours but also acted as a catalyst for Kazakhstan to reassess its foreign policy priorities and alliances. Through a comprehensive examination of these geopolitical vectors, the article aims to unveil how Kazakhstan is maneuvering among these major powers to safeguard its national interests, enhance its regional influence, and capitalize on new geopolitical opportunities.

In doing so, the article employs a multi-dimensional analysis, drawing upon a variety of sources including international relations theory, policy analysis, and empirical data, to offer insights into Kazakhstan's strategic responses to these unfolding geopolitical realities. By identifying new risks and opportunities that have emerged in this context, the paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the implications for Kazakhstan's future direction in Eurasian regionalism and its quest for a balanced and pragmatic foreign policy amidst the new geopolitical conditions.

Keywords: Kazakhstan's foreign policy, global geopolitics, Eurasian Economic Union, regional security, Belt and Road Initiative, Shanghai Cooperation Organization, regionalism, Russia-Kazakhstan relations, China-Kazakhstan trade imbalance, Western partnerships, economic diversification, regional security, trade agreements, geopolitical strategy, multilateral organizations of Central Asia, economic dependency, strategic autonomy, energy cooperation, sovereignty and independence, identity politics.

Transformation of the multi-vector foreign policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the context of geopolitical turbulence

Since gaining independence in 1991, the Republic of Kazakhstan has embarked on a nuanced journey to establish and maintain a multi-vector foreign policy, strategically navigating its relationships with global and regional powers. This policy, rooted in the principles of balance and pragmatism, reflects Kazakhstan's ambition to leverage its significant geographical positioning and abundant natural resources for national development, security, and sovereignty. The cornerstone of this approach has been Kazakhstan's ability to engage with key international players—Russia, China, the United States, and the European Union—without becoming excessively reliant on any single country or bloc. This delicate balancing act has enabled Kazakhstan to carve out a unique and respected position on the global stage, joining international organizations and hosting significant forums aimed at promoting peace, security, and cooperation [1].

The annexation of Crimea by Russia in 2014 and the ongoing conflict in Eastern Ukraine have marked a pivotal moment in the post-Soviet region, challenging

the existing geopolitical order and testing the resilience of Kazakhstan's multi-vector foreign policy. These developments, alongside escalating tensions between Russia and the Western bloc, have placed Kazakhstan in a precarious position, necessitating a careful reevaluation of its historical and strategic ties with Russia. The imposition of economic sanctions on Russia by Western countries has not only affected the Russian economy but also had indirect repercussions for Kazakhstan, given the intertwined nature of their economies and the shared border that facilitates significant trade and energy exchanges.

Amidst these challenges, China's emergence as a dominant economic and strategic partner for Kazakhstan has introduced both opportunities and complexities into the regional geopolitical equation. Through substantial investments in infrastructure, energy, and trade, China has solidified its presence in Central Asia, with the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) positioning Kazakhstan as a critical juncture for trade routes between Asia and Europe. This deepening relationship has spurred economic growth and development in Kazakhstan but

has also raised concerns about the long-term implications of dependency on Chinese investments and the potential for geopolitical leverage [2].

In response to these dynamics, Kazakhstan has sought to enhance its engagement with the collective West, seeking to diversify its economic partnerships and security collaborations. The interest of the United States and the European Union in Central Asia as a strategic counterbalance to Russian and Chinese influences has provided Kazakhstan with additional diplomatic and economic leverage. This engagement has been characterized by efforts to attract Western investment, enhance energy cooperation, and participate in security dialogues aimed at maintaining regional stability and combating terrorism [3][4].

The unfolding war in Ukraine has further complicated the regional and international geopolitical landscape, presenting Kazakhstan with a set of new challenges and considerations. Navigating these turbulent waters requires Kazakhstan to maintain a nuanced and adaptable foreign policy, balancing its historical ties with Russia, the economic opportunities presented by China, and the strategic partnerships available with Western countries. This complex interplay of relationships underscores the importance of Kazakhstan's multi-vector foreign policy as a tool for safeguarding its national interests, enhancing its regional influence, and positioning itself as a key player in the evolving Eurasian geopolitical narrative [5].

As Kazakhstan continues to adapt to these changing dynamics, its ability to maintain a balanced, pragmatic, and flexible foreign policy approach will be crucial. The country's strategic maneuvers in this context not only reflect its immediate responses to geopolitical challenges but also its long-term vision for maintaining sovereignty, securing economic prosperity, and playing a constructive role in regional and global affairs. The evolution of Kazakhstan's foreign policy in the face of ongoing geopolitical turbulence is a testament to its resilience and strategic foresight, offering valuable insights into the complexities of navigating international relations in an increasingly multipolar world.

Russian vector of Kazakhstan's foreign policy

In the intricate tapestry of international relations that defines the post-Soviet space, Kazakhstan's strategic approach to its foreign policy, particularly its engagement with Russia, stands out as a testament to the country's adept navigation through the complexities of regional geopolitics. This narrative delves into the evolution of Kazakhstan's foreign policy vis-à-vis Russia, tracing the historical contours of this pivotal relationship, examining the impact of critical geopolitical events such as the war in Ukraine, and highlighting the guiding principles and documents that have shaped bilateral ties. The analysis aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play, underscoring the challenges and opportunities that have emerged over time.

Since gaining independence in 1991, Kazakhstan has embarked on a journey to establish a distinct identity on the global stage, guided by a multi-vector foreign policy that seeks to balance relations with major powers while safeguarding national interests. Central to

this policy has been Kazakhstan's relationship with Russia, rooted in shared history, cultural affinities, and economic interdependencies. The bilateral relationship has been institutionalized through a series of agreements and treaties, notably the Treaty on Good Neighborliness and Alliance in the 21st Century, signed in 2013, which underscored the commitment of both nations to deepen cooperation across various domains.

Kazakhstan's Foreign Policy Concepts for 2014-2020 and 2020-2030, alongside Russia's own foreign policy guidelines, have consistently emphasized the strategic importance of the Kazakh-Russian partnership. These documents outline a framework for collaboration, highlighting mutual interests in ensuring regional stability, security, and economic prosperity. The establishment of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) in 2015 further exemplifies the economic integration efforts, aiming to facilitate free movement of goods, services, capital, and labor, thereby reinforcing the economic ties between Kazakhstan and Russia [6].

Incorporating the dynamics of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) summits and the evolving stance of Kazakhstan's presidents towards Russia enriches the narrative of Kazakhstan's foreign policy, particularly its intricate relationship with its northern neighbor. These elements reflect the nuanced diplomacy and strategic positioning of Kazakhstan in the broader Eurasian region, especially in light of recent geopolitical shifts.

The EAEU, a significant economic and political bloc in Eurasia, has been a pivotal platform for Kazakhstan and Russia to further their economic integration and cooperation. The summits of the EAEU have, over the years, evolved from mere discussions on economic cooperation to complex forums addressing a wide range of issues from geopolitical challenges to integration processes and international trade dynamics. These summits have served as critical junctures, reflecting the changing contours of Kazakhstan's relationship with Russia and the broader geopolitical environment. For instance, the initial summits focused largely on creating a seamless economic space that would facilitate trade and investment. However, as geopolitical tensions in the region escalated, particularly with the onset of the conflict in Ukraine, the summits began to take on a more strategic significance, addressing concerns over regional stability, security, and the implications of Western sanctions on the economic bloc [7].

Economically, while the EAEU facilitates trade and economic integration among member states, offering Kazakhstan potential growth avenues, there are significant concerns about the long-term implications of such integration. The dominance of Russia's economy within the union, coupled with the potential for economic over-dependence, poses substantial risks to Kazakhstan's economic sovereignty. Moreover, geopolitical tensions involving Russia and the resultant sanctions have had indirect yet tangible impacts on the EAEU's economic environment, further complicating Kazakhstan's economic landscape. These challenges highlight the vulnerabilities associated with deep economic integration within the EAEU framework and suggest that the cons might outweigh the pros in Kazakhstan's continued membership.

From a strategic standpoint, maintaining a diversified and balanced foreign policy is paramount for Kazakhstan. The constraints imposed by EAEU membership on Kazakhstan's ability to independently forge trade agreements and engage with global markets underscore a misalignment with its broader strategic objectives. This misalignment, coupled with the economic vulnerabilities and geopolitical complexities associated with EAEU membership, suggests that Kazakhstan might benefit from reassessing its position within the union. So far, there has been no precedent for leaving the EU among the participating countries, however, there are all possible prerequisites for Kazakhstan to reconsider its participation in this organization and prefer more profitable cooperation with other countries that also have an interest in the republic. Thus, maybe the regional integration would be a better option to form. The CICA, for instance, could reduce the economic and political dependence of Central Asia from Russia [8].

The role of Kazakhstan's presidents in navigating these summits and relations with Russia has been of paramount importance. Nursultan Nazarbayev, Kazakhstan's first president and a key figure in the establishment of the EAEU, played a foundational role in shaping Kazakhstan's multi-vector foreign policy. His leadership was marked by a pragmatic approach towards Russia, seeking to balance Kazakhstan's economic and security interests with its sovereignty and independence. Nazarbayev's participation in EAEU summits was characterized by efforts to advocate for Kazakhstan's interests within the framework of economic integration, while also pushing for respect for the political sovereignty of member states.

With the transition to President Kassym-Jomart Tokayev, Kazakhstan has continued its strategic partnership with Russia within the EAEU framework, albeit with a nuanced recalibration reflective of the changing geopolitical context. President Tokayev has maintained a delicate balance, emphasizing economic cooperation and regional stability while also asserting Kazakhstan's sovereign interests and advocating for a more diversified approach to its foreign relations. Under his leadership, Kazakhstan has approached EAEU summits with a focus on ensuring that economic integration does not come at the expense of national autonomy, and that the Union remains adaptable to the shifting geopolitical landscape, including the ramifications of the war in Ukraine on the region's economic and security environment [9].

Kazakhstan's partnership with Russia spans several strategic projects across energy, infrastructure, technology, and space, each reflecting the countries' intertwined economic and strategic interests. These initiatives, from the proposed nuclear power plant to the Baikonur Cosmodrome lease and cross-border infrastructure enhancements, have ignited a mix of reactions from the Kazakh public and scholarly community, underlining the complexity of balancing national development with environmental and social concerns.

The nuclear power plant project, for instance, has sparked significant debate. While it promises energy security and economic growth, memories of past nu-

clear tests have fueled public fears about safety and environmental impacts. Scholarly critiques emphasize the need for comprehensive impact assessments and exploring renewable energies as safer alternatives. Similarly, the Baikonur Cosmodrome, despite its technological prestige, raises environmental and health concerns among local communities, with calls for better Russian-Kazakh collaboration on mitigation efforts.

Infrastructure projects enhancing connectivity between Kazakhstan and Russia generally receive positive public feedback for their potential economic benefits. However, analytical voices urge caution against economic over-dependence on Russia, advocating for diversified economic partnerships. Energy cooperation, particularly in oil and gas, is welcomed for bolstering economic stability, yet there's a scholarly push for these ventures to align with Kazakhstan's energy independence and environmental goals.

Kazakhstan's engagement with the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) has raised questions about the alliance's efficacy and alignment with Kazakhstan's security needs. Concerns stem from the CSTO's limited crisis response, the influence of Russia possibly overshadowing Kazakhstan's interests, and constraints on Kazakhstan's foreign policy autonomy. These issues underscore the necessity for Kazakhstan to explore strategic alternatives that enhance its national security while maintaining sovereignty.

Alternatives include forging stronger bilateral security partnerships, which offer tailored collaboration without the CSTO's constraints, and deepening involvement with global security organizations like the United Nations or the OSCE, providing a platform for diversified diplomatic engagement. Additionally, investing in national defense modernization enhances Kazakhstan's independent security capabilities. Regional security initiatives with Central Asian neighbors could address shared challenges more effectively, offering a localized approach to security that aligns closely with Kazakhstan's interests.

In essence, while the CSTO forms a part of Kazakhstan's security architecture, the alliance's limitations highlight the need for a more nuanced strategy. By expanding its security portfolio to include bilateral, global, and regional engagements, and by bolstering its own defense capabilities, Kazakhstan can achieve a balanced, flexible approach to security that better serves its national interests and maintains its strategic autonomy in a complex international landscape.

The war in Ukraine marked a watershed moment, introducing new complexities into the bilateral relationship. Prior to the conflict, Kazakhstan and Russia enjoyed a high degree of cooperation and mutual understanding. The ensuing geopolitical upheaval, characterized by Western sanctions against Russia, necessitated a careful recalibration of Kazakhstan's foreign policy. Kazakhstan has strived to balance its longstanding partnership with Russia with its adherence to international law and its desire to maintain productive relations with other global and regional actors. This delicate balancing act is reflective of Kazakhstan's broader foreign

policy strategy, which emphasizes sovereignty, pragmatism, and the diversification of diplomatic engagements.

In the wake of the Ukraine conflict, Kazakhstan has increasingly sought to assert its sovereignty and independence, signaling a nuanced shift in its relationship with Russia. This period has witnessed Kazakhstan engaging more assertively in diplomatic and economic diversification efforts, aimed at reducing over-reliance on any single partner. The challenges posed by the geopolitical shifts have underscored the need for Kazakhstan to navigate a path that respects its historical ties with Russia while also embracing the opportunities presented by a multipolar world.

The risk of economic over-dependence on Russia, especially through mechanisms like the EAEU, is heightened by the potential indirect impacts of Western sanctions against Russia, which could affect Kazakhstan's trade, investment, and overall economic growth. Security concerns also loom large, given the extensive shared border and the possibility of regional security spillovers. Moreover, the imperative to maintain sovereignty and independence is ever-present, as Russia's desire to assert its influence in the post-Soviet space could challenge Kazakhstan's efforts to navigate its path on the global stage [10].

The country's ability to maintain a pragmatic and strategic approach to its relations with Russia, amidst the shifting sands of regional and global politics, underscores the complexities and nuances of international diplomacy in the 21st century. Additionally, this partnership serves as a cornerstone of Kazakhstan's multi-vector foreign policy, allowing it to balance its engagements across global powers, thereby diversifying its international relations and reducing vulnerability to geopolitical shifts. This strategic relationship, if navigated with prudence, positions Kazakhstan to amplify its role on the world stage while safeguarding its national sovereignty and promoting regional stability. Nevertheless, the trend of distancing from the Russian vector took its turn and doesn't show any potential course of keeping the relations on the same level as it was before the occurring War between Russia and Ukraine.

Chinese vector of Kazakhstan's foreign policy

Navigating the intricate landscape of Kazakhstan's foreign policy, the Chinese vector emerges as a crucial component, highlighting a deepening partnership that mirrors the broader geopolitical shifts within Central Asia. This relationship, characterized by strategic cooperation and robust economic ties, has been further cemented through a series of agreements and high-profile visits, underscoring the mutual interests and ambitions of both Kazakhstan and China. These interactions, while marking significant milestones in bilateral relations, also encapsulate the complex dynamics of increasing Chinese presence in the region, bringing to the fore both opportunities and challenges.

In recent years, Kazakhstan and China have signed numerous agreements that span a wide array of sectors, from infrastructure and energy to technology and security. These documents, emblematic of their growing

partnership, reflect a concerted effort to enhance bilateral cooperation. Notably, the advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) stands as a testament to this endeavor, with Kazakhstan positioned as a key transit hub along this modern Silk Road. This initiative has seen China investing heavily in Kazakhstan's infrastructure, including roads, railways, and pipelines, thereby significantly boosting the country's connectivity and access to global markets [11][12]. Beyond infrastructure, energy agreements have also been prominent, with China becoming one of Kazakhstan's largest investors in oil and gas exploration and production, illustrating the strategic importance of Kazakhstan's natural resources to China's energy security.

The economic partnership between Kazakhstan and China, while beneficial, is marked by an imbalance. China's dominant position can lead to arrangements that might not fully serve Kazakhstan's interests, reflecting in the trade dynamics and project implementations that often favor China. For instance, the significant trade turnover between the two countries, reaching around \$18 billion in 2020, highlights their strong economic ties but also points to a trade deficit for Kazakhstan, illustrating the uneven nature of this relationship [13].

The strategic alliance between Kazakhstan and China is a crucial aspect of regional diplomacy within the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), highlighting the diverse facets of their cooperation. This alliance is crucial not only for strengthening the relationship between the two countries but also for reaffirming their dedication to regional peace, economic progress, and collaboration in security matters. China views the SCO as an important means to extend its influence and promote economic integration in Central Asia. Kazakhstan plays a crucial role in connecting China to the abundant resources and markets in the region. On the other hand, Kazakhstan sees the SCO as an opportunity to maintain a balance in its international ties. It can use China's strong economic growth to support its own development, while also working towards the SCO's objectives of fighting terrorism, separatism, and extremism. By engaging in initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) that align with the SCO's goals, both nations have strengthened their economic and security collaboration. This demonstrates the SCO's importance in promoting not only individual national interests but also wider regional cooperation and prosperity [14].

The visits of Chinese President Xi Jinping to Central Asia, including Kazakhstan, have been pivotal, marking critical moments of diplomatic engagement and cooperation. These visits, often resulting in the signing of bilateral agreements, underscore China's strategic interest in Central Asia as a region of growing importance in its foreign policy calculus. President Xi's engagements have not only solidified existing partnerships but also opened avenues for new collaborations, highlighting China's commitment to its Central Asian neighbors. These high-level exchanges underscore the mutual desire to strengthen ties and explore new opportunities for cooperation that extend beyond traditional domains, encompassing areas such as digital innovation and green energy [15].

However, the increasing presence of China in Kazakhstan and the broader Central Asian region is not without its complexities. While the economic benefits of Chinese investment are clear, there are concerns about the potential for economic over-reliance on China. This dependency risk is particularly acute in sectors where Chinese investment is dominant, raising questions about the long-term implications for Kazakhstan's economic sovereignty and diversification efforts. Moreover, the expansion of Chinese interests has sparked discussions within Kazakhstan about the balance between welcoming foreign investment and safeguarding national interests, especially in sensitive sectors such as land ownership and natural resources. The Chinese policy towards the Xinjiang region may also bring complexities into Chinese-Kazakh relations [16].

Public sentiment in Kazakhstan towards Chinese investments and projects has been mixed, with instances of skepticism and opposition reflecting broader concerns about transparency, environmental sustainability, and the terms of investment agreements. These concerns underscore the need for a nuanced approach to managing the partnership, ensuring that it remains equitable and aligned with Kazakhstan's national development goals and public expectations.

Furthermore, the strategic partnership with China, while offering numerous opportunities for regional stability and security cooperation, also requires careful balancing within Kazakhstan's multi-vector foreign policy framework. Kazakhstan must navigate this partnership in a way that complements its relations with other global and regional powers, ensuring that its security and economic interests are not compromised.

In essence, the relationship between Kazakhstan and China is a microcosm of the broader shifts in global and regional geopolitics, encapsulating the dualities of strategic partnership: the opportunities for economic growth and connectivity on one hand, and the challenges of managing economic dependency and public perception on the other. As Kazakhstan continues to engage with China, the emphasis will increasingly be on fostering a partnership that is not only economically beneficial but also sustainable and aligned with Kazakhstan's broader strategic interests and values. This balanced approach will be crucial in navigating the complexities of an ever-evolving geopolitical landscape, ensuring that Kazakhstan leverages its partnership with China to enhance its national development while maintaining its sovereignty and strategic autonomy.

Western vector of Kazakhstan's foreign policy

Kazakhstan's engagement with Western countries is a key facet of its foreign policy, reflecting a strategic commitment to diversification and balanced international relations. This approach emphasizes collaboration in areas critical to Kazakhstan's interests and Western priorities, such as energy security, economic modernization, and regional stability [17].

Kazakhstan has actively participated in various Western-led initiatives and frameworks that underscore this partnership. Notably, agreements with the European Union, including the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) and the Enhanced Partnership and

Cooperation Agreement (EPCA), solidify economic, political, and cultural ties. Kazakhstan's involvement in the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) and interest in initiatives like the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TITR) further demonstrate its commitment to engaging with Western institutions and standards [18].

The essence of Kazakhstan's policy towards the West is geared towards leveraging strategic partnerships to foster economic development and ensure national security, aligning with Western interests in a stable and prosperous Central Asia. Investments from Western entities, particularly in the energy sector, highlight the mutual benefits of this relationship, though specific figures for recent years require direct consultation from official sources [19].

The European Union's Global Gateway strategy presents an intriguing prospect for Kazakhstan, offering a sustainable and values-driven alternative to the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) by China. This approach could afford Kazakhstan greater options in infrastructure development and global connectivity, potentially balancing its economic relations and enhancing its strategic autonomy without increasing dependency on any single power [20].

In summary, Kazakhstan's nuanced foreign policy strategy towards Western countries showcases a proactive effort to diversify its international relations and economic partnerships, underpinned by a desire for balanced development and strategic independence. The engagement with Western initiatives and organizations is central to this approach, highlighting a pathway towards sustainable growth and regional integration.

Conclusion

To sum up, Kazakhstan's foreign policy narrative is one of adept navigation amid the currents of global diplomacy, striving to capitalize on the opportunities presented by its unique geographic and geopolitical position. The nation's approach, characterized by pragmatic engagement with major powers while maintaining a keen eye on its sovereign interests and development goals, sets a precedent for strategic autonomy in the international arena.

As Kazakhstan continues to chart its course through the intricate landscape of international relations, its success will hinge on the ability to sustain this balanced approach. By fostering a diverse portfolio of partnerships and remaining adaptable to the evolving dynamics of global power, Kazakhstan not only secures its place on the world stage but also advances its national vision of prosperity, security, and independence.

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